

methylethylenediamine, dien = diethylenetriamine and trien = triethylenetetraamine.

Low conductance of the complexes in nitrobenzene corresponds to their non-electrolytic nature as indicated by the formula above and suggests that the deprotonation of the NH group of free 2-pyrrolidone has occurred and it has been converted into its uninegative ion, which is capable of acting as a bidentate ligand coordinating through CO and NH groups. However, keeping in view the nature of the ligands used in the study, it is not possible for the ion to act as a bidentate ligand and hence it is suggested that it should have only as a monodentate ligand thus conferring the usual coordination numbers of four on the Cu^{2+} and six on Ni ions. The site of its coordination is the CO group, since in the ir spectra a sharp band appears at 1690 cm^{-1} (CO) stretch, which in free ketone is seen at 1725 cm^{-1} (Refs. 6, 7). The coordination of amines is indicated by the shifts of their relevant ir bands⁸⁻¹². The planar and octahedral geometries of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes are confirmed by their magnetic and electronic data.

The Cu^{2+} complexes are paramagnetic with the magnetic moment around 1.90 B.M. The appearance of a d-d band at 16.00 kK accompanied by two shoulders at 12.00 and 10.50 kK, assignable as ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ transitions respectively, is indicative of planar stereochemistry. The values of μ_{eff} for Ni^{2+} complexes lie in the range 2.97-3.20 B.M. suggesting octahedral stereochemistry. These complexes show three comparatively weak bands at 23.00, 17.50 and 9.50 kK which correspond to the three idealised (O_h symmetry) transitions such as ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) band, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), respectively. The ν_2 as well as ν_3 transitions are found to be broken down in two components which is due to the departure of the symmetry towards pseudooctahedral. The values of the ligand field parameters have been calculated using the well known equation¹³, and it is found that the Dq values for complexes of ligands L are somewhat lower than those L' or L'' which correlates well with the positions of these ligands in spectrochemical series. The β values suggest the presence of sufficient amount of covalent character on the metal-ligand band.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Nickel(II), Copper(II), Palladium(II) and Platinum(II) with Pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and Acetylacetone

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Manuscript received 9 January 1978, revised 23 December 1985,
accepted 3 March 1986

IN continuation of our earlier work¹ on mixed ligand complexes, we now report a slightly different type of mixed ligand complexes of the type described below.

Experimental

[MLL'], type of complexes (where, M = Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} or Pt^{2+} ; L = pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde; and L' = acetylacetone) were prepared by adding pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and acetylacetone to the metal acetate solution in 1:1:1 ratio. The coloured solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. The solid on reaction with an excess of ammonia or alkylamines gave [MLL'A] type complexes (where, A = ammonia or alkylamine molecule) which on refluxing with ethanolamine on a water-bath for 2-3 h gave [MLE.H₂O] type complexes (where, E = ethanolamine). The complexes were recrystallised from methanol.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses. On analysis [MLE.H₂O] type complexes, in addition, indicated the presence of a water molecule per molecule of the complex. These compounds are soluble in common organic solvents. Their negligibly small molar conductance values ($3.2\text{-}7.2\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) suggest them to be non-electrolytic in nature. The Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} complexes are found diamagnetic while Cu^{2+} complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.88$ B.M.) at room temperature.

Fig. 1. Structure of mixed ligand complexes ; R = H, CH₃, or C₂H₅.

The electronic absorption spectra of the mixed ligand Ni²⁺ complexes in methanol gave two bands in the region 610-620 and 535-550 nm which can be assigned to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ³B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ³B_{8g}, respectively. The Cu²⁺ complex (solution) gave one band in the region 635-645 nm which may be assigned to the transition ³B_{1g} → ³E_g. Solution spectra of the Pd²⁺ complexes exhibited three bands in the ranges 440-450, 375-380 and 315-320 nm assigned to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}; ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u}, respectively. The Pt²⁺ complexes also gave three bands in the region 310-320, 350-355 and 420-430 nm assignable to the transitions ¹A₁ → ¹B₁, ¹A₁ → ¹A₂ and ¹A₁ → ³A₂, respectively. These data indicate a square-planar structure²⁻⁵ for the Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pd²⁺ and Pt²⁺ complexes.

In the ir spectra of complexes [MLL'] and [MLL'A], no bands have been observed in the region 3 300-3 100 or 3 600-3 400 cm⁻¹ indicating that hydrogen of the NH group of pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and OH group of acetylacetonate get dissociated on complexation. Spectra of the [MLL'] complexes show bands at 1 630 cm⁻¹ and 1 570 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to aldehydic C=O and C=O of the acetylacetonate, respectively. In the ir spectra of the [MLL'A] complexes (in which R=H), the band at 1 630 cm⁻¹ disappeared and a new band around 1 600 cm⁻¹ C=N of the imine linkage appeared. The band at 1 570 cm⁻¹ C=O of acetylacetonate remains unchanged indicating that it does not undergo condensation. The appearance of the band in the region 3 300-3 100 cm⁻¹ shows the presence of free N-H which was absent in the mixed ligand complexes derived from alkylamines. The ir spectra of the [MLE. H₂O] type complexes show a band around 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH) which confirms the presence of water molecule, and a band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The appearance of two new bands in the region 500-480 and 5'0-560 cm⁻¹ in the above type of complexes suggest the presence of M-O and M-N bondings⁶ in them.

On the basis of the above investigations, the [MLL'], [MLL'A] and [MLE. H₂O] type complexes may be represented by the structures as shown in Fig. 1

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a fellowship to one of them (P.K.K.).

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Stability Constants of Complexes of some Bivalent Metal Ions with *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline and *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline

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Manuscript received 30 July 1985, accepted 17 January 1986

FROM the literature survey on the stability constants it is seen that no work on solution stability constants of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline and *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline has been reported so far. The present investigation is aimed at determining the stability constants of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Cd²⁺, and Mg²⁺ with the above mentioned ligands.

Experimental

The reagents *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,6-dimethylaniline and *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2,4-dimethylaniline, were synthesised by condensing ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 2,6-dimethylaniline and 2,4-dimethylaniline, respectively in equimolar ratios. The products were repeatedly crystallised to get analytically pure compounds. The purity of the compounds was tested by tlc and elemental analysis; m.p. 135 and 99°, respectively.

Calvin-Bjerrum¹ titration technique was used to determine the dissociation constants of the reagents and the formation constants of their metal chelates at 30 ± 0.1° in 75 : 25 (v/v) dioxan-water medium at 0.1 M ionic strength.